

ENTRUST

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D7.4 ENTRUST Website design and release

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:		DEC
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
EU	European Union
URL	Uniform Resource Locators

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the website development for the ENTRUST project (www.entrust-he.eu), defining its objectives and usability. The document outlines the website's structure and content, detailing its initial launch configuration. The website serves as a collaborative platform for sharing knowledge, experiences, best practices, and disseminating project results. This deliverable is closely linked to all the deliverables of WP7, as the ENTRUST website acts as a powerful information flow tool among project entities and is also supported by social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube) that amplify key project messages. It provides comprehensive information about the project, including objectives, partners, use cases, news, and contact details. The website's design prioritizes visual appeal, ease of navigation, and informative content.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Purpose

The purpose of Deliverable D7.4 of ENTRUST is to briefly present the initial setup of the project's website, describing the structure and content of the site at launch. Through this deliverable, all the necessary information of the website is documented, using the initial visual content from the website.

1.2 Relation to other WPs and Deliverables

The current document is closely related to all deliverables of WP7 "Dissemination, Standardization, Exploitation & Impact Creation", since all the activities, events and actions of dissemination, communication and exploitation will be shared through the project's website and social media channels. The aim and context of the WP7 is to engage both external and internal stakeholders effectively, by developing a comprehensive visual identity of the ENTRUST project. The primary objective is to establish a consistent image and enhance brand recognition, ensuring the project is presented and recognized optimally. The visual identity through the website serves as a valuable resource for visitors, providing them with essential information about the project's mission and progress.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

The structure of the document is the following:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the deliverable, its scope and the input it receives from other WPs and deliverables,
- **Chapter 2** provides the website overview and the technical details,
- **Chapter 3** presents the initial content of the website,
- **Chapter 4** concludes the document.

2 Website

2.1 Overview

FN (partner of the project's consortium) has undertaken the design and development of the ENTRUST website. The development activities commenced in M1, and the website was officially launched at the beginning of M2, marking its readiness for full operation.

The website's design prioritizes user accessibility and navigation, ensuring an intuitive experience for visitors. The ENTRUST website plays a central role in online communications, serving as the core platform for sharing information. It acts as the primary hub where visitors can access comprehensive details about the project. On the other hand, supplementary digital and social media channels are utilized to amplify the key messages derived from the project website. These

channels help extend the reach and impact of the project by disseminating important information to a broader audience.

Over time, the website will gradually showcase the project, offering carefully curated non-confidential information such as the project concept, methodology, partner details, core objectives, results, events, and links to relevant EC projects and initiatives. The site will be visually appealing, captivating, user-friendly, informative, pertinent, and up-to-date. It will have a flexible structure that enables dynamic updates and potential restructuring of themes based on specific requirements.

The visual aesthetics of the ENTRUST website are harmonized with the project's logo colour palette, enhancing its overall look and design. The website adheres to the EU's guidelines on usability and accessibility, ensuring an inclusive user experience. It proudly displays the logo of the European Commission, symbolizing its association with EU initiatives.

2.2 URL

The ENTRUST consortium has secured the ownership of the following URL, which is designated for Internet users to access the publicly available project website starting from February 1st, 2023. The responsible partner of the ENTRUST consortium for the website is Future Needs (FN), which will update it and monitor its operation.

URL: <https://www.entrust-he.eu/>

2.3 Technical Details

The technical details of the ENTRUST website are outlined in the following table (Table 1).

The ENTRUST website is built using Wix, which is a popular cloud-based website builder that enables users to create professional website. It provides a user-friendly interface, while it takes care of hosting, security, and technical aspects, empowering users to focus on the design and content of the website [1].

Additionally, the ENTRUST website is strategically designed to ensure convenient access to valuable information about the project for the public. It offers user-friendly features such as the option to subscribe to the ENTRUST newsletter and easily download any publicly available materials. To gain insights into website usage, the site is registered with Google Analytics. This tracking tool enables monitoring of visit counts and analysis of visitor behaviour trends on the project's website. Valuable information, such as the number of users visiting the site, duration of their visits, popular pages and links, and geographical origins of the users, can be obtained through this analytical approach.

Table 1 – ENTRUST Website Technical Details

Domain	https://www.entrust-he.eu/
Content Management System (CMS)	Wix Version 4.0.0

2.4 Website Structure

The structure of the ENTRUST website is straightforward, as depicted in Figure 1. It comprises a public domain that allows visitors to access project-related information, read the latest news and project’s activities, and discover details about the ENTRUST consortium.

As the project progresses, more sections will be added on the website, such as public deliverables, etc.

Figure 1 – ENTRUST Website Structure

3 Website Content

3.1 Homepage

The homepage of the ENTRUST website is structured into several sections that provide essential information about the project, such as a brief introduction, the list of the Use Cases and the partners. In the upper section, there are the basic buttons that ensure the visitors’ navigation on the website. Each one of them are described in the below sections accompanied with the respective figures.

Figure 2 – Homepage

Furthermore, a popup window appears every time someone visits the website, providing a kind reminder of subscribing to the newsletter in order to be updated of the projects whereabouts.

Figure 3 - Popup window

3.2 About

The About page is where ENTRUST Project is being described briefly, providing an insightful overview for the visitors to understand its scope.

Figure 4 - About page

3.2.1 Objectives

The Objectives page is a submenu of About page, where the main objectives of ENTRUST Project are listed.

Objectives

- 01** Dynamic trust assessment and reasoning well-suited for medical devices to establish security and privacy in zero-trust paradigm, considering the latest technological advancements and connection extensions.

- 02** Security- and privacy-by-design through formally defined trust models and protection profiles for minimizing zero-day exploits and threats.

- 03** Post-market surveillance and runtime verification of medical devices trustworthiness through cryptographically verifiable security proofs and efficient attestation.

- 04** Extend the current conformity assessment and certification standards to post-market with the introduction of real-time Conformity Certificates based on runtime verifiable evidence.

- 05** Auditable security and CMD lifecycle management through AI-based misbehavior detection towards building on a Blockchain-based hub of threat intelligence knowledge.

- 06** Integrate and validate the ENTRUST Trust Management Framework for medical devices through real-world pilots to assess its effectiveness.

Figure 5 - Objectives page

3.3 Use Cases

The Use Cases page comprises the four informative descriptions for all the pilots that participate in the ENTRUST Project.

Use Cases	
	<p>Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting</p> <p>This use case will be carried out in the Ankara University Hospital, coordinated by Kardinero, a leading CMD manufacturer in Turkey. Its scope is to validate ENTRUST's security mechanisms and trust assessment over BLE communication, also considering a collaborative fleet of CMDs. Efficiency and stress testing of ENTRUST's attestation enablers will be validated in the strict security and trustworthiness requirements of a real-world medical environment for analyzing attacks during runtime. The provision of real-time conformance certificates will be validated, so that any stakeholder will be able to verify the correct operation of the CMDs.</p>
	<p>Ambient Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living</p> <p>This use case will take place in Norway, where Tellu is one of the major digital health providers providing personal healthcare gateways at patient's home and other healthcare facilities. The Tellu's Health Gateway is responsible for collecting data from various medical devices and sending them to the Cloud services. ENTRUST will enhance the security posture of the remote patient through Verifiable Credentials depicting the operational state per device under a hierarchical SoS environment. ENTRUST's TC-based middleware will support the advanced crypto operations required for remote attestation and communication assurance and its applicability and impact will be evaluated in such heterogeneous environment. Auditability over the update process will be guaranteed using the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure and the enhanced protection profiles.</p>
	<p>Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Well-being of Patients and Carers</p> <p>This use case will be carried out in POLARIS's hospital in Romania and in the Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora in Portugal, involving PARTICLE as the provider of the testbed to support the Patient Transport Services scenario. The monitoring of the CMD networks is a crucial element for both hospitals to comply with all legal and safety requirements. Interconnecting medical devices from different manufacturers to the network infrastructures, storing or retrieving data from EMS services, exposes the hospitals' networks and makes them vulnerable to a wide range of cyber-attacks that can seriously hinder their ability to respond to incidents in lethal consequences timely. In addition, the exchange of patient data from ambulances to the destination hospital expands the security vulnerabilities associated with CMDs and the exchange of patient data between unsecure spaces and the secure hospital IT infrastructure. This use case will focus on the ENTRUST's trust framework and secure data exchange and how it can support the integration of CMDs in the hospital's IT infrastructure, as well as the remote monitoring and maintenance of legacy devices and equipment.</p>
	<p>Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and integrity of Accompanying Data</p> <p>Through this use case the ENTRUST's trust assessment framework will be validated in wearables provided by Sentio Labs in Greece. The use case will focus on data integrity when it come to the communication from the wearable to a mobile device. This is considered critical as the impact of an inaccurate decision may feed an inaccurate medical decision. Also, it is very critical to ensure that the device operates as intended and gathers high-quality data. The same should stand for the entire lifecycle of the product in order to maintain the same quality levels due to the highly sensitive nature of the collected health data. ENTRUST goes a step forward as it can ensure software updates in a zero-trust manner and enhances the privacy of both the device and the patient.</p>

Figure 6 - Use Cases page

3.4 Partners

The Partners page presents a list of all the partners that are included in the ENTRUST project’s consortium, providing a brief description of the organisation’s information, their involvement and contribution to the project, and their logo.

Partners

UNIS (Luxembourg) ^

Uni Systems is one of the most reliable European Information and Communication Technology companies that delivers a wide range of products and services, helping its customers adapt and excel in a rapidly changing and challenging business environment. For more than half a century, Uni Systems remains a strategic partner to financial institutions, public organizations, telecom operators, enterprises and institutions in the European region. It has a proven track record of successful large scale, complex and critical ICT projects in more than 26 countries through its business entities in Athens, Brussels, Bucharest, Luxembourg, Milan and Barcelona.

The company invests in innovation and breakthrough technologies with an established Research and Innovation (RDI) Unit. The RDI Unit keeps the Group abreast of the technological development with participation in significant research activities. Under this mission and objectives, one main and very important RDI activity is to make innovative ideas a reality through Horizon projects. One of the Horizon projects that address the necessity of digital transformation on the medical industry is the ENTRUST Project. Uni Systems will lead WP1 activities and will be responsible for the project coordination as well as for the Quality, Risk and Innovation Management of the project. Also, Uni Systems will actively contribute to the Technical Requirements and the Reference Architecture of the project (WP2), to the Security and Trust Attestation Models for Runtime Verification as well as to the SW and Trust Controls Update for Remote CMDs (WP4). Regarding WP5 activities, Uni Systems will actively participate in the Blockchain Design and Services Specification, with the Enforcement of Distributed Trust Framework and Smart Contracts for the Lifecycle Management of Medical Devices as well as with the CMD Evidence Monitoring Collection. Additionally, Uni Systems will be involved in WP6 with the Integration Design and Testing Plan as well as with the Use Cases Management, Deployments and Validation. Finally, regarding the activities in WP7, we will contribute to the Open-Source Roadmap for CMD Trust Reference Implementation as well as to the Exploitation & Business and Sustainability Planning.

Eindhoven University of Technology (the Netherlands) v

SINTEF (Norway) v

Figure 7 - Partners page

3.4.1 Synergies

The Synergies page is a submenu of Partners page, where all the collaborations with other EU funded projects will be presented, accompanied with a short description, their logo and social media accounts.

Figure 8 - Synergies page

3.5 Library

The Library page of the ENTRUST website is where the visitors will be informed of the projects' progress. All the updates and material related to the project will be shared in this page, which is divided in the respective submenus and described in the following section.

In this page, more submenus will be added, like the option of the deliverables preview for the interested visitors of the website, and dissemination material.

3.5.1 All Posts, Blogs, News, Events

Under the Library page, the website provides the submenus of All Posts, Blog, News and Events, where all the relative items will be placed depending on their nature. In this pages, the website's visitors will have the opportunity to be aware of the ENTRUST project's participation to conferences, workshops or events, and to read the partners' blogposts that are related to their contribution to the project.

Figure 9 - Library page

3.6 Contact

The Contact page includes a contact form, where the visitors will add their personal contact details (First-Last name, email address) and write a message, which will be sent to the project’s contact point. People who submit a contact form as well as the subscribers of the project newsletter have to accept the terms of use. At the same time, there are listed some contact information (email addresses) and the social media buttons, which redirect the visitors to the channels of communication that the project has (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube).

Figure 10 - Contact page

When visiting the website, visitors are presented with a cookies notification, ensuring transparency and compliance with data protection regulations. This notification allows users to make an informed decision about accepting or declining the use of cookies. Within the same box, users have the option to view the cookie settings, granting them more control over their data. Additionally, the privacy policy is conveniently provided, giving visitors easy access to understand how their personal information is handled and protected. By integrating the cookies notification with the privacy policy, the website promotes transparency, user empowerment, and adherence to privacy standards.

Figure 11 - Cookies Notification

Figure 12 - Cookies Settings

ENTRUST

Ensuring Secure & Safe Connected Medical Devices Design with Zero Trust Principles

Privacy Policy

The ENTRUST project is committed to protecting your privacy and is developing technology that gives you the most powerful and safe online experience. This Statement of Privacy applies to the Web Site of the HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13 ENTRUST project (Grant Agreement No. 101095634) and governs data collection and usage. The Web Site falls under the responsibility of the ENTRUST Consortium and is concerned with the dissemination and exchange of information about the research conducted in the course of the project and the outcome of this work. By using the Web Site of the ENTRUST project, you consent to the data practices described in this statement.

Figure 13 - Privacy Policy

3.7 Footer Section

In the footer section of the project’s website, some useful information is listed such as key facts of the project and acknowledgement of funding from the EU under the Horizon Europe programme.

Figure 14 - Acknowledgement

There is also a subscription form to the ENTRUST’s newsletter, where the interested visitors can add their email address and receive updates and news related to the project.

Figure 15 - Subscribe to Newsletter

At the end, social media buttons and contact details of the project coordinator are provided.

Figure 16 - Social Media Buttons and contact

4 Conclusion

The primary objective of the ENTRUST website is to facilitate efficient information exchange among all project stakeholders. It serves as a platform for targeted dissemination of information to relevant parties. As the project advances, the website is expected to undergo regular updates to ensure effective online dissemination and incorporate emerging project outcomes. These updates will focus on enhancing usability for end-users and involve content contributions from consortium members. Over time, the ENTRUST project website will be enriched with additional information, including audio-visual content, to provide a comprehensive overview of project progress.

References

- [1] "Your Website, Your Business, Your Future | wix.Com." Wix.Com, www.wix.com/.

